

Speculation on the Hamilton-Jacobi Theory, Special Relativity and Quantum Mechanics

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Hamilton-Jacobi theory was developed in classical mechanics before special relativity was known. In the literature one often sees derivations of the Schrodinger equation based on Hamilton-Jacobi theory (e.g. (1)). On the other hand, according to (2), Hamilton-Jacobi theory makes use of a Lagrangian function, $L(v,x,t)$ such that $dL/dv \text{ partial} = p$ (momentum). Momentum is defined in Newtonian mechanics, but it is only an approximate manner. The full definition follows from special relativity which is based on viewing a particle at rest from frames moving with different constant $-v$ (for example). Thus, the notions (and formulas) of E and p for a free particle follow from special relativity, so the Lagrangian must be linked to special relativity otherwise the definition of momentum does not even exist. If one considers a free particle, then we argue that one should not imply that quantum mechanics follows from Hamilton-Jacobi theory, but rather try to see it follow from special relativity.

Secondly, we have noted that special relativity is linked to different frames moving at various constant $-v$. We have argued in previous notes that free particle quantum mechanics follows from degeneracies in $A = -Et + px$. A particle at rest with mass m_0 , however, may be made to move physically by applying force. Thus, the physical process of applying this force (acceleration) should be responsible for the probabilistic \hbar/p and \hbar/E seen in quantum free particle, i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ as well as the different x', t' (from the rest frame x, t). We argue that this is interesting because $\exp(ipx)$ is also created in other situations such as in an infinite well where one has an $\exp(ipave x)$ and in one-dimensional reflection-refraction where $\exp(ip_2 x)$ in a medium n^2 (index of refraction) is the representation for a photon interacting with atoms/molecules and then free space in that medium.

Hamilton-Jacobi Theory

One often sees in the literature derivations of the Schrodinger equation from Hamilton-Jacobi theory, e.g. (1). In other words, it seems there exists a wish to connect quantum mechanics to classical mechanics. The Hamilton-Jacobi theory, however, makes use of a Lagrangian function, $L(x,v,t)$, (see (2)), such that:

$$dL/dv \text{ partial} = p \text{ (momentum)} \quad ((1))$$

P (momentum) exists in Newtonian mechanics, but is only an approximate value. The full definition of p :

$$P = mv/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \text{ (one dimension)} \quad ((2))$$

follows from special relativity. This seems to imply that the Lagrangian and Hamilton-Jacobi theory really have their roots in special relativity. Thus, we argue that if one seeks quantum mechanics of a free particle, one should look for it in special relativity and not necessarily Hamilton-Jacobi theory.

In particular, if one had no notion of energy and p (momentum) for a free particle, but only considered a rest mass, m_0 , at rest at $x=0$ at t , one could create a Lorentz transformation for $x=0, t$ such that $x'/t'=v$. This means that x' and t' actually differ from x, t . Furthermore, the particle will be seen to be moving from a frame with constant $-v$, so one may transform $(0, m_0)$ using the same Lorentz matrix used to transform $(x=0, t)$ with $x'/t' = v$, thus creating, E and p :

$$E = m_0 c \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \quad \text{and} \quad p = m_0 v / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \quad ((3))$$

Here c is really a constant upper bound speed and one makes use of the notion that the transformation must link (p, E) to m_0 , i.e. the two ultimately must represent the same thing, i.e. ultimately the transformation with the metric $(1 \ 0)$

$$(0 \ -1)$$

must leave the dot product constant. This leads to $E^2 - p^2 = m_0^2 c^4$ ($c=1$). ((4))

Perhaps a simple way to see this is to say that m_0 is equivalent to both (p, E) and $(-p, E)$. To create an expression which does not depend on the sign of p , one may use $(p+E)$ and $(-p+E)$ and multiply, which is equivalent to $m_0^2 c^4$.

Ultimately, we suggest that the definition of p and E for a free particle arise from special relativity, so this underlies Hamilton-Jacobi theory. We suggest that quantum mechanics for a free particle should ultimately follow from special relativity directly and not indirectly from Hamilton-Jacobi, if in fact it does follow from this route.

We have suggested in previous notes that the degeneracy of the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$ leads to time and space gradations:

$$t = t_0 + n \hbar / E \quad \text{and} \quad x = x_0 + n \hbar / |p| \quad \text{where } n \text{ is an integer} \quad ((5))$$

From this one may obtain $\exp(ipx)$ as a possible probability which respects AND situations: $\exp(ip_1 x) \exp(ip_2 x) = \exp(i(p_1 + p_2)x)$ which is the same as conservation of momentum. At the same time, px represents a uniform distribution in a length $p = \hbar / \text{wavelength}$.

Special Relativity and the Notion of Force

In the previous section, we argue that free particle quantum mechanics follows from special relativity, which in turn is based on viewing a rest mass m_0 from different frames moving with $-v$ constant. We note, however, that physically one may take a rest mass and apply a force to move it. Thus, physically, $\exp(ipx)$, the new x', t' and the quantum time and spatial resolutions ((5)) must occur through the application of this force. In other words, $\exp(ipx)$ is a consequence of the force acting on a rest mass.

It may be, however, that the force is really responsible for changing x', t' from (x, t) and creating gradations as the form $\exp(ipx)$ appears in many general cases. For example, if one has an infinite potential well, then one has:

$$.5 \{ \exp(i p a v e x) + \exp(-i p a v e x) \} \quad (\text{center of well at } x=0) \quad ((6))$$

$\exp(ipave x)$ is really composed of many $\exp(ipx)$ s yet, has the same mathematical form as each of its constituent $\exp(ipx)$ s.

In the case of one dimensional reflection-refraction at an n_1 - n_2 index of refraction junction, a photon is described by $\exp(ip_2 x)$ in the n_2 medium. Physically, however, the medium is composed of atoms/molecules and free space and interactions of the photon with the atoms/molecules occur, so $\exp(ip_2 x)$ seems like an average description.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in the literature there are numerous derivations of the Schrodinger equation from Hamilton-Jacobi theory, i.e. quantum theory from classical theory. Hamilton-Jacobi theory (2) uses a Lagrangian function which satisfies $dL(v,x,t)/dv \text{ partial} = p$. P (momentum), however, is only fully defined through special relativity. Thus, the Lagrangian and Hamilton-Jacobi theory really have their root for a free particle in special relativity. We thus suggest that one seek quantum mechanics in special relativity directly. In previous notes, we have argued that the degeneracy of $A = -Et + px$ leads to the quantum time and spatial resolutions ((5)) and then free particle quantum mechanics.

Special relativity's Lorentz transformation may be obtained by considering a free particle at rest (rest mass= m_0) at $x=0$ at t . If it is viewed from a frame moving at $-v$ (constant) then there must be a new x', t' such that $x'/t' = v$. Physically, however, one may apply a force to a rest particle. We thus suggest that the force must change x, t to x', t' and introduce the quantum resolutions ((5)) because it is the physical agent of the motion.

References

1. Kyprianidis, A. Hamilton-Jacobi Theory and Quantum Mechanics I (1988)
[www.sciencedirect.co ... /abs/pii/0375960188902903](http://www.sciencedirect.com/abs/pii/0375960188902903)
2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hamilton%E2%80%93Jacobi_equation